

Effect of calcium-rich additions on the mechanical and microstructural properties of metakaolin-based geopolymer concrete cured in ambient sub-Saharan climate

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ABSTRACT

One of the remaining challenges to extend the field of applications of geopolymers is their relatively weak performance under ambient curing conditions, which could be resolved by the addition of calcium-rich products. However, depending on the nature of these calcium-rich products, their effects may differ from a physico-mechanical or microstructural point of view. This study assesses the effect of different calcium-rich additions on the mechanical properties and microstructure of metakaolin (MK) based geopolymer concrete activated by NaOH solution 12 M and cured in ambient conditions of sub-Saharan climate. The MK was partially substituted by different types of calcium-rich additions, namely calcium carbide residue (CCR), quick lime (QLM), slaked lime (SLM), and ordinary Portland cement (OPC). After curing at ambient temperature (30 °C) for 7 to 90 days, concretes were tested to evaluate their compressive strength. The microstructural properties were also investigated. The results showed that the substitution of MK by calcium-rich products leads to an improvement in mechanical strength of geopolymer concrete compared to plain MK-based geopolymer concrete. However, early-age performances differ according to the nature of the calcium product: QLM and SLM have an overall accelerating effect on early-age strength development, while CCR and OPC generally develop strength slowly. Moreover, microcalorimetry analysis reveals that the substitution of MK by calcium products leads to a global decrease in total heat released, regardless of the type of calcium product. Furthermore, it was observed that the exothermic peak was delayed and generally spread out, resulting in more prolonged curing of the pastes and consequently higher mechanical strength. The microstructural analysis shows that the reaction products mainly consist of 2 types of zeolites (Zeolite A and Zeolite X) and low-Ca C-(N)-A-S-H gel. The more heat the calcium-rich product tends to release, the faster the geopolymerization reactions and vice versa. This study demonstrates the feasibility to design metakaolin-based geopolymer concretes at room temperature to reach up to a compressive strength of 30 MPa for engineering applications.

Keywords:

Ambient curing
Calcium-rich additions
Geopolymer concrete
Mechanical properties
Metakaolin
Microstructure

1. Introduction

Geopolymers and alkali-activated materials (AAMs) are becoming increasingly popular in the scientific community as alternatives to hydraulic Portland cement-based binders. In developed countries, the main motivation for research on alkali-activated materials in general and geopolymers in particular is the need to find a less polluting alternative

to Portland cement for its CO₂ emissions. The abundance of industrial waste, for which the landfill disposal issue is far from being resolved, is also one of the reasons behind the growing interest in these alternative materials. Indeed, given their important content in amorphous alumina and silica, certain industrial by-products such as blast furnace slag (BFS) have shown their potential as aluminosilicate precursors for the manufacture of geopolymers.

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In developing countries, the interest in alternative materials such as geopolymers is more in line with the search for high-performing and affordable materials sourced from locally-available raw materials. These novel materials can provide an alternative to ordinary Portland cement, which is still not affordable to a large majority of the population. To date, the clay potential of developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (Burkina Faso), is barely exploited [1]. The common applications of these clay materials are in banco adobe bricks, compressed earth bricks, fired bricks and pottery, thus perpetuating certain traditional and cultural knowledge [2–4].

In order to find suitable materials rich in amorphous alumina and silica, recent studies have identified clay quarries rich in kaolinite, making them ideal for geopolymer production [1,2,5,6]. Generally, a material that contains high amount of reactive silica and alumina such as metakaolin could potentially be used for producing geopolymer. Indeed, kaolinitic clays are well known as pozzolans, and their reactivity is enhanced when calcined at optimum temperatures between 650 and 800 °C, resulting in a change from a crystalline phase, with very low reactivity, to a highly reactive amorphous form characterized by a disorganized internal structure. Numerous studies have shown that the calcination temperature can influence the reactivity of the MK material. Glid *et al.* [7] observed good reactivity of metakaolin when calcinated during 12 hours at temperatures around 550 °C. On the other hand, when the calcination temperature reached 800 °C, they observed a decrease in the reactivity, with a consequent delay in the appearance of geopolymers' reaction products, even after activation in alkaline medium. In recent studies, authors tend to set the calcination temperatures and the calcination time of kaolinitic clays at around 750°C and 3 hours respectively [8]. Above 800°C, a recrystallization of the amorphous phase occurs and thus making the calcined clay less prone to react correctly [9].

Highly rich in silica and alumina, with a low calcium content, MK is comparable to class F fly ash in terms of the composition, reactivity, and reaction product when subjected to geopolymerization [5,6,10]. Numerous studies have demonstrated that MK-based geopolymers can achieve good performance when a heat curing of around 60 °C, is applied in addition to other factors such as the combination of alkali silicate and NaOH as activator; or the combination of MK with calcic aluminosilicates such as BFS [11–14]. When MK is used as an aluminosilicate-source with NaOH solution as the activator, the reaction products are essentially zeolites and N-A-S-H type hydrates with a very porous microstructure, and, in some cases, the associated mechanical performances are relatively low [7,15,16]. While the thermal curing combined with alkali silicates, such as sodium silicates, improves the reactivity of metakaolin during the geopolymerization process; these approaches may not be adapted to the desired reduction in carbon footprint and the thermal curing that would be required in-situ applications.

As with Class F fly ash, the reactivity of MK during geopolymerization at ambient temperature is enhanced when calcium sources are introduced, within certain limits [17]. Indeed, Ca²⁺ cations can play various roles in geopolymer matrices. They improve the reactivity of low-calcium or calcium-free aluminosilicates by accelerating paste setting and contributing to the formation of new phases in the matrix, thus contributing to its densification [18–20]. It has been observed that, when introduced in sufficient quantities into a geopolymer matrix, cationic exchanges occur between the Na⁺ of the sodium aluminosilicate hydrate (N-A-S-H) gel and the Ca²⁺ of the calcium compound to form a new phase of C-(N)-A-S-H type, which may coexist with the N-A-S-H; although, the latter is predominantly formed within the aluminosilicate gel. The use of calcium-rich materials in MK-based geopolymer systems is also justified by the pozzolanic nature of MK [21]. Indeed, in case the geopolymerization reaction is incomplete, the free MK in the system is likely to combine with the hydrated calcium oxides (portlandite) present to form hydrated calcium aluminates and silicates (C-A-H and C-S-H respectively) following a latent reaction as

summarized in Eqs. 1–2. Due to the latency of these reactions, their beneficial effects on microstructure, durability, and mechanical behaviors are perceptible only after relatively long curing periods or over the extended term (curing time beyond 28 days).

A wide range of calcium-rich materials have been identified to have a positive effect on the geopolymerization of metakaolin at room temperature. Aluminum cement in geopolymers accelerates the setting of the geopolymer material due to the contribution of the aluminum network and the heat of hydration contained in the cement [19]. Huo *et al.* have shown that the use of 10 % OPC in geopolymers promotes complete dissolution of the aluminosilicate, enhanced polymerization through the formation of calcium aluminosilicate hydrate C-(A)-S-H type gels, coexisting with N-A-S-H type gels which result exclusively from the geopolymerization reaction [22]. They proposed that the hydroxyl ion in the high alkaline solution may first react with the soluble calcium of OPC, leading to the formation of Ca²⁺, Ca(OH)⁺ and Ca(H₂O)(OH)⁺ in the alkaline medium. Sore *et al.* showed a positive effect of OPC on MK-based geopolymer concrete cured at ambient temperature. Their study has demonstrated that, when cured at ambient temperature, up to 20 % OPC can improve the overall mechanical and durability properties of metakaolin-based geopolymer; but this type of cement is not common in some region of the world especially those where there is a lack of raw material for clinker production, due to its high content of clinker [23].

CCR, a portlandite-rich by-product, has also shown its potential in geopolymer systems. Zhao *et al.* observed that CCR combined with sodium carbonate could generate a strongly basic medium with a pH close to 14, which is sufficient for geopolymerization [24]. They also demonstrated that CCR could lead to an increase in setting time, a reduction in heat of hydration and an improvement in mechanical performance. CCR releases Ca²⁺ ions into the medium and the Ca/Si ratio of the gel is improved, favoring the formation of C-S-H-type reaction products. When unreacted, it acts as a filler, resulting in a denser matrix in both cases. As an industrial by-product, CCR is not free of impurities that can interfere with the reactions which take place. In fact, the carbonates found in CCR can inhibit the dissolution reactions of the aluminosilicate precursor, thus delaying the setting of the geopolymer [24,25]. Du and Yang demonstrated that CCR had a positive effect on the mechanical strength of clay materials, in particular clayey plant ash, at an optimum CCR content of 16 % [26]. A previous study on MK-based geopolymer concrete blended with calcium carbide residue (CCR) showed an improvement in compressive strength when the curing temperature was increased by 10 °C (from 20 to 30 °C). However, it did not study microstructural properties or long-term physico-mechanical properties [27].

Other industrial calcium products such as hydrated lime have shown their potential for geopolymerization due to their level of purity and relatively higher calcium content than CCR. Hydrated lime (SLM) is one of the high-calcium products that was used by ancient civilizations for building structures. Compared with CCR, hydrated lime is less subject to impurities. Consequently, its proportion in the reaction medium can be kept relatively low, not to build up an excess that could interfere with the reactions. When used in a geopolymer system, lime promotes geopolymerization not only through the contribution of calcium to the reaction medium, but also through the pozzolanic reaction in combination with natural pozzolans such as metakaolin (Eqs. 1 and 2). The hybrid lime-pozzolan-geopolymer system showed better mechanical performance and durability than a system solely made up of pozzolanic reaction products [28,29]. Quicklime (QLM) is also a credible option that has received little attention in the literature for its potential to improve geopolymerization at room temperature. Some few studies do not take advantage of the heating potential of quicklime, as they tend to proceed with heat-curing; even when quicklime is used in geopolymer

formulation [30]. Indeed, the hydration of quicklime produces an exothermic reaction whose heat could contribute to the curing of geopolymers at ambient temperature. Chakraborty observed an improvement in mechanical performance when quicklime is used during alkali-activation at an optimum rate of 20 %, resulting in mechanical strengths of around 31 MPa [31].

Despite the growing interest in recent studies on the addition of calcium products to geopolymers, it is still difficult to determine which of these additions would be most effective for geopolymer manufacture, given the wide variety of formulation conditions. In addition, most previous studies have focused more on the mechanical aspects and certain additives, such as silicate additives, which can change the nature of the reaction products.

In this study, the effect of the substitution of metakaolin with various calcium additives (CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC) on the mechanical and microstructural properties of a metakaolin-based geopolymer concrete activated by sodium hydroxide solution was investigated under room-temperature curing conditions in the context of sub-Saharan climate. The average ambient temperature and relative humidity were set at 30 °C and 50 % respectively, to reflect the realities of the sub-Saharan climate, which is particularly well known for its high average temperatures and low relative humidity [27,32].

2. Materials and experimental methods

2.1. Binders

2.1.1. Aluminosilicate materials

The kaolin clay used was obtained from Saaba (12°22'44.9''N; 1°24'38''W), a locality in the city of Ouagadougou. It was dried, crushed, sieved at 80 µm, and then calcined at a heating rate is 10 °C/min up to 700 °C and kept constant for 3 hours. The obtained metakaolin is predominantly composed of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ at a cumulative rate of 96.2 % (Table 1). Clay's calcination is essentially characterized by dehydroxylation and reorganization of Si-O-T bonds (T = Si or Al) within the material. These transformations are detected in the infrared analysis (Fig. 1) by the disappearance of peaks around 3600 cm⁻¹ (H-O-H bonds) and a rearrangement of peaks around 1060 cm⁻¹ (Si-O-T) and 798 cm⁻¹ (Si-O-Al). XRD analysis (Fig. 2) of the raw and calcined clays. This shows a disappearance of kaolinite peaks marking its transformation into metakaolin. TGA analyses carried out on raw clay and calcined clay (Fig. 2) also show the transformation of kaolinite peaks marked by the absence of humps between 450 °C and 750 °C on calcined clay.

2.1.2. Calcium-rich additions

The CCR used is an industrial waste from a local company specializing in the production of acetylene. Once collected, CCR appears in the

Table 1

Chemical composition of different calcium-rich additions: MK, CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC.

Oxides	MK (%)	CCR (%)	QLM (%)	SLM (%)	OPC (%)
SiO ₂	54.3	3.90	0.27	0.38	22.8
CaO	0.07	60.1	75.5	74.8	54.4
Al ₂ O ₃	42.7	1.72	0.08	0.09	6.64
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.61	0.42	0.03	0.05	4.57
K ₂ O	0.15	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.54
Na ₂ O	0.07	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.53
MgO	0.05	0.17	0.27	0.27	3.10
Mn ₂ O ₃	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08
TiO ₂	0.19	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.41
F	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12
SO ₃	0.00	0.28	0.03	0.03	2.42
P ₂ O ₅	0.05	0.02	0.12	0.14	0.45
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02
LOI	1.89	33.3	23.6	24.1	3.86

Fig. 1. FTIR analysis of raw clay, MK, CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC.

Fig. 2. XRD analysis of raw clay, MK, CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC, K: kaolinite; Q: quartz Silicon oxide (PDF 01-077 SiO₂ α-SiO₂); P: portlandite (PDF 00-044-1481 Ca(OH)₂ syn); C: calcite (PDF 00-047-1743 CaCO₃); G: gypsum (PDF 01-070-0983 Ca(SO₄)(H₂O)₂); An: anorthite (PDF00-041-1486 CaAl₂Si₂O₈ ordered); Al: alite (PDF 00-031-0301 Ca₃SiO₅).

form of more or less compact lumps. It is coarsely ground with a hammer, dried in the sun, crushed, and sieved with an 80 µm sieve, then stored in containers protected from any contamination. The chemical composition of the materials presented in Table 1 shows that the CCR contains a high proportion of CaO (over 66 %).

The QLM (quicklime) comes from the local market. It is supplied in the form of whitish granules of varying sizes (between 10 and 50 mm in diameter) in 20-kilogram plastic boxes, which are kept dry. These granules are first broken by a metal hammer into small pieces that can be fed into the RETSCH_RS_200 electric planetary disc mill (grinding is carried out at 700 rpm for 2 minutes). The powder obtained is then sieved at 80 µm and stored in closed containers, away from any contamination.

The SLM (hydrated lime) is obtained by the complete hydration of QLM. The hydration process consists of introducing water onto the quicklime granules until no more exothermic reaction is released. It is then left in water for 24 hours to ensure complete hydration of the quicklime particles. The collected paste is then oven-dried at 105 °C to remove the excess moisture. It is then ground in a planetary disc mill at 700 rpm for 2 minutes. The collected powder is then sieved at 80 µm and stored in containers protected from any contamination.

The OPC (ordinary Portland cement) is a CEM-II/B-M (P-L) 42.5 N corresponding to the 42.5 MPa strength class, with ordinary short-term strength. It contains a mixture of limestone and natural pozzolan and its chemical composition (Table 1) reveals that it is mainly composed of CaO (54.4 %) and SiO₂ (22.8 %).

XRD analysis reveals that CCR is rich in Portlandite and Calcite, while SLM is essentially composed of Portlandite with a few traces of Calcite. QLM is mainly composed of Calcium oxide with barely visible traces of portlandite and calcite. The XRD analysis of Portland cement reveals that it consists mainly of Alite (C₃S) with traces of Gypsum, Dolomites, Calcites and Anorthites. The 3 % MgO content in the cement (Table 1) is therefore linked to the dolomites detected by the XRD analyses. The thermogravimetric analyses also show that CCR contains relatively high amount of calcite when compared to other calcium products.

2.1.3. Alkaline solution

Sodium hydroxide, concentration of 12 M, is used as the activator solution as recommended by previous studies [1]. It is obtained by dissolving 99 % pure NaOH pellets in distilled water, 24 hours prior to the use. The process of the preparation of 1 litre of 12 M NaOH solution consists of the dissolution of 480 g of the pellets of NaOH in 1 litre of distilled water.

2.2. Aggregates

The sand and the granitic gravel were purchased locally in the city of Ouagadougou. The sand is mainly extracted from river beds, while the gravel comes mainly from privately-owned granite crushing sites. The aggregates have particle sizes in the ranges of 0–5 mm and 5–10 mm, respectively, for sand and gravel (Fig. 5). They were washed and dried at 105 °C in an oven for 24 hours and stored in container to avoid any contamination. The granulometric analysis shows that the sand has a well-distributed particle size with a fineness modulus of 2.28 and HAZEN uniformity coefficient (Cu) of 3.33, which makes it particularly suitable for the production of concrete; while the gravel has a uniform particle distribution (Cu = 1.43 < 2).

2.3. Mix design and characterization methods

2.3.1. Concrete mixing, casting and curing

The composition of the geopolymer concrete is presented in Table 2. The formulation was inspired by the literature, notably that of Cao *et al.* [19]. The reference formulation is a geopolymer concrete whose precursor is solely composed of metakaolin powder (100 % MK) activated with the 12 M NaOH solution; sand and gravel and is noted 100MK. Subsequently, part of the metakaolin is substituted by the high-calcium material (CCR; QLM; SLM and OPC) at a rate of 5 % up to 25 % or until optimum strength is reached. Some previous studies have shown that the optimum substitution percentage for calcium compounds is around

Fig. 3. Thermogravimetric analysis: TG curves of raw clay; CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC.

Fig. 4. Thermogravimetric analysis: DTG curves of raw clay; CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC.

Fig. 5. Particle size distribution of aggregates.

Table 2
Mix design of the geopolymer concretes.

Material (kg/m ³)	Calcium product [CCR; OPC; QLM; SLM] content (%)					
	0	5	10	15	20	25
MK	350	332.5	315	298	280	262.5
Ca-based additions	0	17.5	35	53	70	87.5
NaOH pellets	126	126	126	126	126	126
Water	229	229	229	229	229	229
Sand	723	723	723	723	723	723
Gravel	958	958	958	958	958	958

15–50 % for certain calcium products [11,33,34]. The nomenclature follows the same rule as for the substitution rates in the concretes. For example, the concrete containing 15 % of the metakaolin substituted by quick lime will be called 15QLM and the concrete noted 25CCR would correspond to the one in which 25 % of the total mass of metakaolin is replaced by CCR.

The amount of activating solution is kept constant, though in such a way as to ensure good workability of the concrete while taking care not to introduce excessive water into the concrete. In fact, water simply acts as a solvent for various reagents. Its presence in relatively large quantities during the formulation of geopolymers is likely to compromise their performance from a mechanical and durability point of view. It is found in the pores and can easily evaporate, creating additional

porosities that can affect geopolymer materials [35]. In this study, the ratio (MK + Ca-rich material)/NaOH is kept constant at 0.5 for all concretes to ensure good workability without compromising their performance as observed in previous studies [23,27].

Concrete design involves mixing the aggregates (gravel + sand) and the precursor (MK + High calcium compound). Once the mixture has been homogenized, the sodium hydroxide solution is added gradually, while mixing continually. The molds used are cylindrical (\varnothing 50 mm \times H 100 mm). They are filled with dough and placed on a shock table (twice 60 strokes) to expel the trapped air. The specimens are unmolded 24 hours after setting.

Concrete specimens and pastes are stored at 30 ± 5 °C and a relative humidity of 50 ± 10 % then covered to limit water loss until the desired curing date. The nomenclature of the concrete is related to the nature and the percentage of the calcium product that it contains.

2.3.2. Paste mixing and curing

The microstructural analyses were carried out on pastes with the same composition as the concretes, except for the aggregates (sand and gravel). The composition of the pastes is shown in the ternary diagram in Fig. 6. As the portion of activating solution is constant, all formulas are on the same line corresponding to the ratio (MK + Ca. Material)/NaOH = 0.5 on the pseudo-ternary diagram in Fig. 6.

After mixing, the pastes were molded in sealed cylindrical plastic boxes (\varnothing 30 mm \times H 60 mm). They are stored in the same ambient conditions as the concrete (30 ± 5 °C; 50 ± 10 % relative humidity). In order to limit carbonation risks when exposed to ambient air, the pastes was demolded only when the desired maturation time is reached. Fig. 6 presents the pseudo-ternary diagram of MK; NaOH; calcium product) for the geopolymer paste.

2.3.3. Mechanical characterization method

At the desired curing date, mechanical properties were assessed through compressive strength determined using a PROETTI hydro-electric press, which has a capacity of 300 kN with a load rate of 0.25 kN/s until failure. For each mix design, the recorded value was the average of 3 measurements. The compressive strength [MPa], is the ratio of the load at failure [N], and the cross-section area [mm²] of the specimen.

2.3.4. Microstructural characterization methods

To obtain powders for TGA/DTG, FTIR and XRD analysis, the hardened pastes were taken out of the molds, wet-sawed with an electric saw

and lyophilized. They were then ground in a planetary disc mill at 700 rpm for one minute. The powder obtained after grinding is sieved at 63 μ m and stored in carefully sealed boxes in a desiccator. Lyophilization was carried out at 50 °C for 48 hours to freeze all moisture from the pastes, using the CRIOS 55 CRYOTEC freeze-dryer.

The XRD test was carried out with the D8 Advance BRUKER diffractometer using Cu K α radiation (λ K α = 0.154186 nm) with an acquisition step of 0.02° (2 θ) between 4° and 70°. The data collected was analyzed with Eva software and crystallized phases were identified by comparison with ICDD (International Center for Diffraction Data) PDF (Powder Diffraction Files) standards.

Infrared spectra of the raw materials and the geopolymer pastes were accessed through a Perkin Elmer UATR1 Frontier type spectrometer with data collected and processed by OMNICTM software.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted on a METTLER TOLEDO TGA 2-type instrument between 30 and 1050 °C under an argon atmosphere. A pre-crushed and sieved geopolymer paste of approximately 40 mg with a maximum particle size of 63 μ m was tested. The heating rate was 10 °C/min.

Electron microscopy observations were made using a JEOL JSM-6380LV scanning electron microscope on carbon metalized geopolymer samples. These microscopic observations were performed on polished and fractured sections. The dry polishing was performed using, first, abrasive discs and then polishing discs with silicon carbide coatings. The samples' cross-sections were metalized with a carbon film for electron conduction. The quantification by weight of oxides was performed by elemental analysis using energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM + EDX).

In order to access the hydration heat flow properties of the geopolymer pastes, an eight-channel isothermal calorimetry microcalorimeter (TAM Air) was used. The samples were kept in the apparatus during 100 hours at a temperature of 30 °C in order to match the curing temperature of the geopolymer concretes.

3. Results and discussion

This chapter will address the results of the study. The first section will concern the mechanical properties of the geopolymer concretes. The next sections will address the effect of each calcium product on the mineralogical and microstructural properties of the geopolymer pastes. The last chapter will discuss comparatively the results of the mineralogical and microstructural properties of the optimal pastes.

3.1. Effect of calcium-addition on the mechanical properties of geopolymer concretes

Fig. 7 shows the evolution of compressive strengths at 7, 14, 28, and 90 days for different geopolymer concrete formulations. The reference concrete (100MK) seems to reach its maximum compressive strength early. In fact, after reaching 11 MPa at 7 days, the compressive strength increases slightly between the 7th and 14th days (+13.6 %). After the 14th, there is no more increase in strength which is maintained at 12.5 MPa at the 28th and the 90th days for this concrete. Indeed, when geopolymer concrete is formulated using a low or calcium-free aluminosilicate reaches the maximum strengths in relatively short timeframes, however, this phenomenon tends to be amplified when they are thermally cured [36,37].

The addition of calcium compounds had various effects on the evolution of the strength of geopolymer concrete over time, depending on the nature of the calcium substitute. When metakaolin is substituted by CCR, the 7-day strength is lower than the 100MK reference concrete. There is a progressive increase in strength over time for all samples containing CCR, in contrast to the 100MK reference whose strength no longer increases beyond the 14th. From the 14th day, the addition of CCR significantly improves mechanical properties from 5 % upwards. In fact, at 90 days, with 5 % of CCR, mechanical strength increases from

Fig. 6. Pseudo ternary diagram (MK; NaOH; calcium product) of geopolymer paste.

Fig. 7. Compressive strength of the geopolymer concrete at different curing days (7, 14, 28, 90 days).

14.5 to 20.6 MPa, i.e. improving by more than 42 % compared to 100MK reference concrete. The optimal substitution rate of metakaolin by CCR is 15 %. At 90 days, when the substitution rate reaches 15 % CCR, the improvement is over 113 % more than the reference concrete 100MK, from 14.5 to 31 MPa. Beyond 15 %, CCR leads to a decrease in long-term concrete strength. Indeed, compared to 15CCR at 90 days, compressive strength decreases from 31 to 23.3 MPa (-24.8 %) and from 31 to 18.2 MPa (-41.3 %) respectively for concretes containing 20 and 25 % CCR. Considering that most common structures can be made with 20 MPa concrete, a substitution of 5–20 % would be the recommended range for CCR usage in MK-based geopolymer systems.

When metakaolin is substituted by the hydrated lime SLM, the 7-day results show that the samples containing less than 15 % SLM have lower strengths than the 100MK reference concrete; while higher substitution rate tends to increase these early mechanical properties. Similarly to CCR, there is a progressive increase in resistance over time for all samples containing SLM, in contrast to the 100MK reference. The substitution of metakaolin by SLM up to 10 % increases the compressive strength of the concrete. Beyond this optimal level, the excess lime in the matrix becomes detrimental to the concretes. The maximum strength obtained at 90 days is 22 MPa corresponding to 51.7 % improvement when compared to the reference concrete. When compared to 10SLM, further SLM addition led to a decrease in compressive strength by -7.7 % and -28.2 % for 15SLM and 20SLM respectively. In this case, a substitution of 10–15 % would be the recommended range for SLM usage in MK-based geopolymer systems in order to obtain concretes with compressive could reach 20 MPa.

When metakaolin is substituted by QLM, the 7-day results show that all the samples exhibit higher compressive strengths than the 100MK reference concrete. The maximum strength obtained at 28 days is 23 MPa, which roughly corresponds to more than the maximum strength obtained for SLM at 90 days. The heat of hydration of QLM would therefore serve to accelerate geopolymerization. Between 14 and 28 days, concrete containing 5 % QLM did not show a significant increase in strength. However, between 28 and 90 days, there was a significant increase in strength, from 21 to 30 MPa (+44 %). The same trend can be noticed in concretes containing 10 % QLM, where the strength improvement between 14th and 28th days (+5 % of 14th day strength) is negligible compared to the strength improvement between 28th and 90th days (+29.3 % of 28th day strength). This suggests that reaction products continue to be develop at a slow rate beyond 28 days. Moreover, the optimum substitution rate of metakaolin by the commercial quicklime ranges between 5 % and 10 %. In fact, the exothermic reaction would cause significant water loss when QLM is used above

10 %. This would have the effect of weakening the concrete matrix beyond 10 % substitution. In fact, during the testing process, concrete containing 15 % QLM tended to spall. This would be one of the reasons behind the sudden decrease in 90 days' compressive strength from 30 to 19.5 MPa (-35 %) when the quicklime substitution rate is increased from 10 % to 15 %. Therefore, a substitution of 5–10 % would be the recommended range for QLM usage in MK-based geopolymer systems. In contrast to the 20 % optimum obtained in previous studies [31], the lower substitution rate of 15 % QLM needed to reach the optimum strength in the present study could be due to the differences in the nature of the precursor, which was not metakaolin as in the present study.

When metakaolin is substituted by the Portland cement, the 7-day results show that the samples containing less than 15 % OPC have lower strengths than the 100MK reference concrete; while higher substitution rate tend to increase these early mechanical properties. The compressive strength of all formulations containing OPC at 20 % or below shows a remarkable improvement between day 7 and day 14. For instance, the compressive strengths of formulations 5OPC, 10OPC, 15OPC and 20OPC increased respectively from 7.5 to 18 MPa (+140 %); from 6.5 to 19 MPa (+192 %); from 11 to 25.5 MPa (+131.8 %) and from 13.2 to 19 MPa (+43.9 %) between the 7th and 14th day. Further improvements were observed between the 14th and 28th day, with an average of +37.7 % increase for these 4 previous formulations. However, after day 28, most OPC-containing formulations seem to stop reacting. At 90 days, except the 10OPC formulation, which improved by +15 %, the other formulations retained their 28th day strength. Thus, Portland cement not only improves the overall mechanical performance of geopolymer concrete, but also accelerates reaction rates to the point where the most significant part of these reactions would occur during the first 28 days. This observation marks the main difference between OPC and other calcium products characterized by a clear improvement in long-term mechanical properties (between days 28 and 90). This is mainly due to the chemical composition of OPC compared to that of the other calcium products. Indeed, although OPC is predominantly composed of CaO (54.4 %), it also contains a significant proportion of SiO₂ (22.8 %), known for its beneficial effect on geopolymerization. Previous studies have shown that additional SiO₂ in a geopolymer system accelerates reactions and enhances mechanical performance [38, 39]. Furthermore, the optimum OPC substitution rate is between 10 % and 20 %, and the maximum strength observed at 90 days is 31.3 MPa. Beyond 20 % substitution, excess OPC cement leads to a significant decrease in compressive strength. As OPC substitution increases from 20 % to 25 %, compressive strength at 90 days decrease from 28.6 to 14.5 MPa (-49.3 %). Consequently, substitution rates between 5 % and

20 % would be more suitable for the use of OPC in metakaolin-based geopolymer systems.

Overall, the addition of these calcium products seems to generate long-term mechanical changes. For instance, the strength of concrete containing 15 % CCR improved by over 60 % between days 28 and 90, from 19 to 31 MPa. The 5 % QLM concrete shows a similar increase, from 21.8 to 30.5 MPa (+40 %) between days 28 and 90. The increase in strength between 28 and 90 days is 18 % for concrete containing 15 % SLM. Therefore, the evaluation of mechanical properties beyond 90 days would be highly advisable in order to access the maximum value and the time frame at which these properties would reach the optimum.

The presence of Portlandite in the base material seems to have a positive effect in the overall reactivity of the system by increasing the alkalinity in the reaction environment and could be a controlling factor of the reactivity in some geopolymer systems as described by previous authors [40].

Although all these calcium-rich substitutes have a positive effect on mechanical strength, the existence of optimum proportions indicates the upper limits that must not be exceeded, depending on the nature of the product as shown by previous studies. Cong and Mei [41] had shown that the optimal substitution percentage of CCR and hydrated lime is around 12 % which is close to the results obtained in the present study.

Previous research has also shown that above a certain level of substitution of the geopolymer precursor by a CaO-rich material, the mechanical strengths decreases due to either excessive desiccation or inhibition of the geopolymerization reaction. The inhibition of the geopolymerization reaction is believed to occur when the excessive calcium-material released in the reaction medium tends to increase the distance between the initial oligomers thus delaying or preventing new crosslinks to be formed [42].

3.2. Effect of calcium-addition on the mineralogical and microstructure of geopolymer pastes

3.2.1. Effect of CCR addition on the mineralogical properties

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show respectively the results of FTIR analysis of paste containing 15CCR at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days) and pastes containing different amount of CCR at 90 days curing dates. Absorption peaks around 3350 cm^{-1} correspond to free or bonded H-O-H groups. The absorption band around 1645 cm^{-1} corresponds to the vibrations of the O-H or H-O-H groups of the water in the geopolymer matrix [43], [44]. The peaks observed around 650 and 745 cm^{-1} correspond to the vibrations of Si-O-Al bonds involving Al atoms in a tetrahedral coordination [45]. The peaks observed around 1400 cm^{-1} correspond to the vibrations of C-O groups indicating the presence of carbonate in the geopolymer paste. The main peak observed for the absorption band between 948 and 970 cm^{-1} corresponds to the vibrations of the symmetrical and asymmetrical elongation of the Si-O-Si and

Fig. 8. FTIR analysis of 15CCR at 7, 28 and 90 days.

Fig. 9. FTIR analysis of CCR pastes at 90 days.

Si-O-Al bonds and highlights a major footprint of the geopolymer matrix since the bands corresponding to the Si-O-Si and Si-O-Al bonds of the metakaolin are around 1061 cm^{-1} [46–48]. Even though the exact position of the peak corresponding to these bonds seems to be dependent of the Si/Al ratio in the base materials [48].

At 7 days, the peaks around 660 and 745 cm^{-1} are not sufficiently visible for 15CCR paste. They start to appear clearly on day 28. This suggests an evolution of geopolymerization reactions leading to the formation of new chemical bonds beyond day 7 when CCR is used in MK-based geopolymer system because those peaks correspond to the vibration of Si-O-Al bonds involving Al atoms in a tetrahedral coordination [45,48].

The results show a shift of the peaks corresponding to geopolymerization products to the right as the geopolymer curing period increases for CCR additions. For the paste containing 15CCR, the main peak observed at 947 cm^{-1} at 7 days shifts to 953 and 960 cm^{-1} at 28 and 90 days of curing respectively. This could indicate an evolution in the pastes' structure, leading to the improvements in mechanical properties observed when the curing time is extended from 7 to 90 days.

The evolution over time indicates that, like the portlandite peaks observed around 3641 cm^{-1} , the peaks observed around 1400 cm^{-1} associated with carbonates tend to decrease as the curing period increases. This could indicate either a progressive consumption of the calcium initially available in the form of CaOH_2 and CaCO_3 , or rather an evolution of the matrix over time, becoming less prone to carbonation.

The results of the infrared analyses in Fig. 9 indicate that an increase in CCR content in the paste generates a stronger signal of the presence of carbonates, which could indicate that the carbonates might have come from the base material CCR used for the formulation. Furthermore, the nature of the reaction products remained globally the same no matter the amount of CCR involved in the formulation.

Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 shows respectively the results of XRD analysis of paste containing 15CCR at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days) and pastes containing different amount of CCR at 90 days curing date. XRD analysis essentially reveals the presence of two main reaction products: zeolite X and zeolite A, with a predominance of one or the other at younger ages, depending on the amount of calcium substitution product. The introduction of calcium compounds into the formulations results in significant changes in the footprint of reaction products, especially from 2θ comprised between 4 and 38° . In particular, the peaks associated with zeolites decrease when metakaolin is substituted by CCR. This decrease in peak amplitude is particularly noticeable as the substitution rate of CCR increases. It can be seen that increasing the substitution rate from 5CCR to 25CCR leads to a significant reduction in the height of peaks observed around 2θ of 7 , 9 , 16 , 22 and 30° . The decrease in these peaks could be linked to the formation of amorphous products that are difficult to detect with X-rays alongside the initially well-crystallized zeolites A and X when calcium is introduced in the reaction medium.

Fig. 10. XRD analysis of 15CCR at 7, 28 and 90 days, X: Zeolite X Sodium aluminum silicate hydrate (PDF 01-073-6104 $\text{Na}_{92}(\text{Al}_{92}\text{Si}_{100}\text{O}_{384})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{100.8}$); A: Zeolite A Sodium Aluminium Silicate hydrate (PDF 00-039-0222); P: portlandite (PDF 00-044-1481 $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ syn); He: Heulandite-Ca ($(\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_7\text{O}_{18.6}\text{H}_2\text{O})$ PDF 00-021-0131).

Fig. 11. XRD analysis of CCR pastes at 90 days, X: Zeolite X Sodium aluminum silicate hydrate (PDF 01-073-6104 $\text{Na}_{92}(\text{Al}_{92}\text{Si}_{100}\text{O}_{384})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{100.8}$); A: Zeolite A Sodium Aluminium Silicate hydrate (PDF 00-039-0222); He: Heulandite-Ca ($(\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_7\text{O}_{18.6}\text{H}_2\text{O})$ PDF 00-021-0131).

In addition, Fig. 11 revealed that while zeolite A was initially difficult to detect at 7 and 14 days of maturation, in contrast to zeolite X, it had strongly crystallized by day 90, even to the point that zeolite A peaks become more visible than those of zeolite X. This would indicate that zeolite X had strongly crystallized by day 7, in contrast to zeolite A, whose effective crystallization, marked by more pronounced peaks at 90 days, occurred beyond day 28 when CCR was used to substitute MK. As time passes, the appearance at 90 days of a new reaction product, notably He zeolite (Heulandite calcian), detectable at $2\theta = 11.5^\circ$, indicates that the formation of reaction products may continue even in the long term (beyond the 28th and 90th days). Moreover, the hump observed for 2θ ranging from 25 to 40° becomes progressively flatter as the maturation time increases. Typical of highly reactive amorphous aluminosilicate materials, this hump was initially observed on metakaolin (Fig. 2) and its reduction is thought to be the consequence of the progressive use of zeolite reaction products, whose chemical formulas reveal a succession of silicon and aluminum atoms initially detached from the aluminosilicate during the dissolution phase in the alkaline solution.

Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 show respectively the results of TGA analysis of paste containing 15CCR at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days) and pastes containing different amounts of CCR at 90 days. The results reveal a gradual mass loss between 30 and 1000°C , with a total loss of 24.5–27 % for CCR pastes. These mass losses are comparable to other

Fig. 12. TGA analysis of paste containing 15CCR at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days).

Fig. 13. TGA analysis of CCR pastes at 90 days.

geopolymers whose reaction products are essentially zeolites. Musyoka *et al.* observed a mass loss of around 20 % on zeolites A and X during thermogravimetric analyses [49].

Furthermore, the TGA analyses show the presence of 4 main transformation zones for pastes matured at 90 days. The main transformation peak observed around $180\text{--}200^\circ\text{C}$ corresponds to weakly bound water or structural water. The main peak is preceded by a shoulder at around 125°C and for pastes matured during 7 days and corresponds to free water contained in the micropores, due to the freeze-drying process prior the TGA test was unable to remove completely. The structure of geopolymers has been widely studied, and it is now generally accepted that water molecules are not involved in the structure itself, as they are in cement hydration [35]. Previous studies reported that this main peak at around $100\text{--}200^\circ\text{C}$ could be assigned to C-A-S-H gel [40].

The third and fourth transformation zones are located between 550 and 750°C and between 780 and 1000°C respectively and correspond to the denaturation of weakly to strongly crystallized calcites. In addition to these 4 main transformation peaks observed on the pastes after 90 days of curing, another main transformation peak can be observed on the pastes after 7 days of curing: the peak observed between 420 and 480°C corresponds to the transformation of portlandite [30]. Only observable at 7 days for pastes incorporating CCR, the absence of this peak from the 28th day of curing could reflect the dissolution of portlandite in

the reaction medium or its gradual consumption in the pozzolanic reaction with metakaolin.

3.2.2. Effect of slacked lime addition on the mineralogical properties

Fig. 14 and Figure show respectively the results of FTIR analysis of paste containing 10SLM at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days) and pastes containing different amounts of SLM at 90 days curing date.

The results in Fig. 14 show a shift of the peaks corresponding to geopolymerization products to the right as the cure period increases for SLM additions similarly to the shift observed on CCR pastes when the curing period increased from 7 to 90 days. On 10SLM paste, the main peak observed at 948 cm^{-1} at 7 days shifted to 952 and 960 cm^{-1} at 28 and 90 days respectively. This could indicate an evolution in the pastes' microstructure, leading to the improvements in mechanical properties observed when the curing time is extended from 7 day to 90 days.

At 7 days, the band around 745 and 660 cm^{-1} are not sufficiently visible for paste containing the slacked lime. Similar to pastes containing CCR, those bands start to clearly appear on day 28, showing the evolution of geopolymerization reactions beyond day 7 for these various additions.

The evolution over time indicates that, like the portlandite peaks observed around 3641 cm^{-1} , the peaks observed around 1400 cm^{-1} associated with calcites tend to decrease as the curing period increases. This could indicate either a progressive consumption of the calcium initially available in the form of CaOH_2 and CaCO_3 , or an evolution of the matrix over time, becoming less prone to carbonation. Furthermore, an increase in slacked lime content led to a more visible signal of calcite peak in the pastes.

Fig. 16 presents the results of XRD analysis of paste containing 10SLM at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days). The substitution of Metakaolin by slacked lime led to the formation of zeolite A as early as day 7, alongside a minor trace of zeolite X. These results also show a fairly pronounced presence of the hump characteristic of the unreacted part of the amorphous aluminosilicates for 2θ between 25 and 40° at early days of curing. At 7 days, we can also observe the presence of peaks associated with portlandite around 2θ equal to 18 and 28° . These portlandite peaks are no longer detectable at day 28, and their disappearance is accompanied by the appearance of new zeolite peaks associated with zeolites A and X. The appearance of these new zeolite peaks from day 28 is accompanied by a remarkable reduction in the hump for 2θ ranging from 25 to 40° , demonstrating the transformation of amorphous aluminosilicate into other reaction products with different characteristics to metakaolin. The disappearance of portlandite peaks could suggest its dissolution, leaving calcium ions to integrate the microstructure. Indeed, the addition of calcium materials into a geopolymer system promotes the overall reaction of the amorphous aluminosilicate. Calcium also acts as a nucleation center and contributes to the charge balance in the geopolymer system [22,50].

Fig. 14. FTIR analysis of 10SLM at 7, 28 and 90 days.

Fig. 15. FTIR analysis of SLM pastes at 90 days.

Fig. 16. XRD analysis of 10SLM at 7, 28 and 90 days, X: Zeolite X Sodium aluminum silicate hydrate (PDF 01-073-6104 $\text{Na}_{92}(\text{Al}_9\text{Si}_{100}\text{O}_{384})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{100.8}$); A: Zeolite A Sodium Aluminium Silicate hydrate (PDF 00-039-0222); P: portlandite (PDF 00-044-1481 $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ syn); Q: Quartz syn (PDF 01-079-1910 SiO_2).

Fig. 17 shows the results of TGA analysis of paste containing 10SLM at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days). The results show the presence of 4 main transformation zones similar to those observed on CCR pastes and therefore corresponds to the same components discussed

Fig. 17. TGA analysis 10SLM at 7, 28 and 90 days.

in that section. However, the total mass loss ranged between 19.5 % and 22.5 % for SLM pastes. The Portlandite peak observed between 420 and 480 °C at 7 days is barely visible at 28 days. Its complete absence in 90-day paste confirms once again the consumption and integration of calcium in the geopolymer system.

Although it is generally accepted that water does not play a fundamental role in the structure of geopolymers, the data tend to show that its structure seems to evolve between days 7 and 28. Indeed, the free water departure peak which was observed at 125 °C on the 7th day has evolved to 200 °C on the 28th day and remained unchanged since then. This might reflect a change in microstructure as revealed by XRD analysis on this paste (Fig. 16) where additional zeolite peaks appeared between the 7th and the 28th days. The modification of the microstructure generally led to the modification of pore structure. As consequence, the departure of trapped water in the pores could exhibit different behavior as the curing time is prolonged due to the refinement of the pore structure. As the peak observed at around 100–200 °C could correspond to C-A-S-H as reported in previous section, its modification between the 7th and the 90th days of maturation could indicate an evolution in the structure of the C-A-S-H when the maturation time increases.

3.2.3. Effect of quicklime addition on the mineralogical properties

Fig. 18 and Fig. 19 show respectively the results of FTIR analysis of paste containing 10QLM at different curing dates (7, 28, and 90 days) and pastes containing different amounts of QLM at 90 days curing date. The evolution over time (Fig. 18) indicates that similar behavior as QLM in terms of the evolution of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.

Unlike the two previous calcium products (CCR and SLM), the paste containing 10QLM, shows the presence of the Si-O-Al absorption band around 745 cm^{-1} and 660 cm^{-1} as early as day 7, revealing a more rapid formation of reaction products corresponding to these absorption bands when quicklime is used compared with other calcium products. Therefore, the quicklime could have an overall accelerating effect on the geopolymerization process.

Fig. 20 and Fig. 21 show respectively the results of XRD analysis of paste containing 10QLM at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days) and pastes containing different amounts of QLM at 90 days curing date.

In contrast to CCR, the use of QLM as a substitute for MK showed that the formation of the 2 types of zeolites effectively occurs from an early age, through well-marked peaks. Thus, at 7 days, the analysis reveals a predominance of peaks associated with highly crystallized zeolite A alongside zeolite X, which is most likely in the early stages of its formation. The detection of fairly well-marked peaks as early as 7 days would indicate increased reactivity caused by the incorporation of quicklime and corroborates the high mechanical strength at 7 days for 10QLM, reflecting the acceleration effect of quicklime in geopolymerization reaction when compared to CCR addition.

Fig. 18. FTIR analysis of 10QLM at 7, 28 and 90 days.

Fig. 19. FTIR analysis of QLM pastes at 90 days.

Fig. 20. XRD analysis of 10QLM at 7, 28 and 90 days, X: Zeolite X Sodium aluminum silicate hydrate (PDF 01-073-6104 $\text{Na}_{92}(\text{Al}_{92}\text{Si}_{100}\text{O}_{384})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{100.8}$); A: Zeolite A Sodium Aluminum Silicate hydrate (PDF 00-039-0222); P: portlandite (PDF 00-044-1481 $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ syn); Q: Quartz, (syn PDF 01-079-1910 SiO_2).

Fig. 21. XRD analysis of QLM pastes at 90 days, X: Zeolite X Sodium Aluminum silicate hydrate (PDF 01-073-6104 $\text{Na}_{92}(\text{Al}_{92}\text{Si}_{100}\text{O}_{384})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{100.8}$); A: Zeolite A Sodium Aluminum Silicate hydrate (PDF 00-039-0222); Q: Quartz (syn PDF 01-079-1910 SiO_2).

Fig. 22 and Fig. 23 shows respectively the results of TGA analysis of paste containing 10QLM at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days) and pastes containing different amount of QLM at 90 days. The results show the presence of 4 main transformation zones similar to those observed on CCR and SLM pastes and therefore correspond to the same

Fig. 22. TGA analysis of paste containing 10QLM at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days).

Fig. 23. TGA analysis of QLM pastes at 90 days.

components namely $H_2O/C-A-S-H$; portlandite, and calcites. However, the total mass loss ranged between 21 % and 23 % for SLM pastes. The portlandite peak observed between 420 and 480°C at 7 days flattened out at 28 days. Its complete absence in 90-day paste confirms once again the consumption and integration of calcium in the geopolymer system.

3.2.4. Effect of OPC addition on the mineralogical properties

Fig. 24 and Fig. 25 show respectively the results of FTIR analysis of paste containing 10QLM at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days) and pastes containing different amounts of QLM at 90 days curing date. At 7 days, the band around 745 and 660 cm^{-1} are still not fully formed for the 10OPC paste. They start to appear clearly on day 28, showing the evolution of geopolymerization reactions beyond the 7th day when metakaolin is substituted by the Portland cement. The absence of these bands at early age, linked to the subsequent missing reaction products, could justify the low mechanical strengths observed at 7 days for OPC-containing pastes. Furthermore, the results in Fig. 25 show that increasing the Portland cement content from 5 % to 25 % in the geopolymer paste composition does not lead to any change in the reaction products produced from the FTIR analysis point of view.

Fig. 26 shows the results of XRD analysis of paste containing 10OPC at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days). As for CCR, the addition of 10OPC leads to a delay in geopolymerization reactions. At 7 days,

Fig. 24. FTIR analysis of different 10OPC paste at 7, 90 28 and days.

Fig. 25. FTIR analysis of different OPC pastes at 90 days.

Fig. 26. XRD analysis of 10OPC at 7, 28 and 90 days, X: Zeolite X Sodium Aluminum silicate hydrate (PDF 01-073-6104 $Na_{92}(Al_{92}Si_{100}O_{384})(H_2O)_{100.8}$); A: Zeolite A Sodium Aluminum Silicate hydrate (PDF 00-039-0222 ($Na_{96}Al_{96}Si_{96}O_{384})(H_2O)_{216}$); Q: Quartz, syn (PDF 01-079-1910 SiO_2); C: calcite (PDF 00-047-1743 $CaCO_3$).

reaction products are almost invisible for 2θ between 4 and 29°, except for a trace of zeolite A observed at 7° (2θ). Above 29°, XRD reveals that at 7 days, the reaction products detectable by X-rays are essentially Zeolite A and calcium carbonate. The characteristic hump of the initial aluminosilicate MK observed between 25 and 40° (2θ) reveals that the reactions are not yet complete, and that MK still predominates in the reaction medium. In contrast to all other calcium additions, the absence of portlandite in the 10OPC geopolymer paste at 7 days suggests the absence of cement hydration in the reaction medium. By day 28, the

initial aluminosilicate hump between 25 and 40° had flattened remarkably, with the appearance of new zeolite A and X peaks for 2θ between 4 and 40°, justifying the increase in mechanical strength observed between days 7 and 28. Between days 28 and 90 of curing, the differences observed consist in an increase in the peaks already formed at day 28, demonstrating the continuity of the reactions, but at a much slower rate than between days 7 and 28. At the same time, the change in mechanical strength between the 28th and 90th day of maturation is relatively less than that observed between the 7th and 28th day.

Fig. 27 shows the results of TGA analysis of paste containing 100PC at different curing dates (7, 28 and 90 days). The main transformation peak observed around 180–200 °C corresponds to weakly bound water or structural water. The main peak is preceded by a shoulder at around 125 °C and corresponds to weakly-bonded water contained in the micropores. The results show the presence of transformation zones corresponding to weakly bonded water (125 – 200 °C) and CO₂ (550–750 °C; 780 – 1000 °C). The total mass loss ranged between 20 % and 21.5 % for OPC pastes. The evolution of water departure (125–200 °C) exhibit similar behavior as compared to previous 10SLM paste between the 7th and the 28th days, thus revealing a refinement of the pore structure.

The portlandite peak (420 – 480 °C) is not as clearly marked as for the previous calcium products. It is in accordance with the XRD analysis (Fig. 26) which did not demonstrate any portlandite presence in 100PC paste regardless of the curing time.

This could indicate that cement hydration would not fully take place under the conditions of strong alkalinity required for good geopolymerization (hypothesis 1); or that the portlandite released during cement hydration was consumed up fairly quickly to form C-S-H (hypothesis 2) following the pozzolanic reaction process described above (Eqs. 1 and 2). Indeed, cement hydration initially releases portlandite, which is used by pozzolans such as metakaolin for the production of hydrated calcium aluminum silicates (C-A-S-H) [22].

If such reaction takes place, given the excess of metakaolin pozzolan in the medium, all the portlandite produced during cement hydration could be entirely consumed, which explains why it was not detected by various analyses. However, the detection of portlandite on the other calcium products at 7 days could mean that even if the pozzolanic reaction were to take place, it would not be instantaneous, as proposed in the second hypothesis which suggests a fairly rapid consumption of the portlandite released by the Portland cement.

In view of these observations, the first hypothesis on the non-hydration of Portland cement under these conditions of extreme alkalinity seems the most plausible. This assertion seems to be in line with the previous observations on mechanical strength in Fig. 7. In that section, it was observed that the 100PC formulation showed lower

early-age strengths than the 100MK reference concrete. If cement hydration has taken place in the early-age system, it should contribute to an improvement in early-age strength. In addition, when the Portland cement content is increased beyond 20 %, there is a decrease in mechanical performance, in contrast to what would have occurred if cement hydration had taken place. Previous study has reached similar results by describing the hydration of Portland cement in caustic media as abnormal since no cement hydration products could be found in such an alkaline environment. It is believed that there is a decline in calcium solubility at high alkaline media which tends to prevent the precipitation of portlandite [51].

Furthermore, the FTIR analysis presented earlier revealed that even for an addition rate of 25 % OPC, the reaction products were not fundamentally different from those of 50PC, 100PC or 150PC. In particular, it was noted that the characteristic geopolymer bumps present around 960, 745 and 664 cm⁻¹ remained the same for all Portland cement-containing formulations (50PC, 100PC, 150PC, 200PC and 250PC). Given the effectiveness of the geopolymerization reactions for all these formulations, the reduction in mechanical performance associated with the addition of extra cement may be justified by the non-hydration of the cement, confirmed by the absence of portlandite in the TGA analyses. These results are in line with those of Martinez-Ramirez and Palomo, who observed a delay in cement hydration in a highly alkaline environment, which even tends to dissolve C-S-H when it forms [52,53]. A similar observation was made by Huang, who noted that in the long term, strongly alkaline environments were detrimental to cement hydration, even though at a young age, these alkaline environments favored the dissolution of the C₃S contained in the cement [54].

3.3. Discussion of the mineralogical and microstructural properties of optimum concrete geopolymer designs

Fig. 28 shows the results of FTIR analysis of optimal pastes at 90 days. FTIR analysis reveals the presence of calcites only for pastes containing calcium products CCR; QLM; SLM and OPC. However, the presence of carbonates is much more pronounced in pastes containing 15CCR. Carbonation of geopolymers is a phenomenon that generally takes place when CO₂ from the ambient air comes into contact with dissolved calcium or sodium to form calcium or sodium carbonate. However, under certain exposure conditions, such as an environment very rich in carbon dioxide, the geopolymer pore solution is likely to contain other carbonation products such as natron (Na₂CO₃(H₂O)₁₀), nahcolite (NaHCO₃) or trona (Na₃H(CO₃)₂) [55–57]. In this study, the calcium substitute products in general and CCR in particular initially contain calcites (Fig. 1; Fig. 2; Fig. 3 and Fig. 4). It is unlikely, under the current maturation conditions, that the calcites detected originate from carbonation reactions with ambient air. This assertion is further

Fig. 27. Thermogravimetry analysis of 100PC at 7, 28 and 90 days.

Fig. 28. FTIR analysis of optimal pastes at 90 days.

supported by the absence of carbonates on 100MK paste cured under the same conditions.

The results of the infrared analyses also indicate that an increase in calcium product in the paste generates a stronger signal of the presence of carbonates, which could indicate that the calcites might have come from the base materials. In addition to the shift observed with increasing curing time, it was also observed that the addition of calcium products causes a change in the structure of the reaction products, marked by a shift from the main peak observed at 970 cm^{-1} for the 100MK reference paste to 960 cm^{-1} when MK is substituted by any of the calcium products. Similar work by Ma *et al.* showed that the addition of calcium hydroxide to a metakaolin-based geopolymer resulted in a shift of the main peak observed around $1077\text{--}1029\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The authors noted that this shift to lower wavelengths would indicate better polymerization [58]. Other researchers, on the other hand, have observed that better polymerization may be reflected in a shift towards longer wavelengths. In their work, Kaze *et al.* noted that an increase in silicate modulus led to a better reaction, marked by improved mechanical strength and a shift of the main peak observed from 970 to 977 cm^{-1} [43].

Fig. 29 shows the results of XRD analysis of optimal pastes at 90 days. XRD analysis essentially reveals the presence of two main reaction products: zeolite X and zeolite A, regardless of the calcium product used. The introduction of calcium compounds into the formulations results in significant changes in the footprint of reaction products, especially from 2θ comprised between 4 and 38° . In particular, the peaks associated with zeolites decrease when metakaolin is substituted by calcium-rich products. The decrease in these peaks could be linked to the formation of amorphous products that are difficult to detect with X-rays alongside the initially well-crystallized zeolites A and X when calcium products is introduced in the reaction medium, as observed by other authors [59].

The presence of crystalline phases in all formulations for 2θ of 26.6° corresponds to quartz (PDF 01-079-1910 SiO_2) from metakaolin. This shows that the quartz contained in the metakaolin is totally inert during geopolymerization, but could play a role as a filler which positively reinforces the structure.

Previous studies have focused on the formation of zeolites through geopolymerization reactions [49,60]. Onutai *et al.* showed that zeolites A and X are the main products formed when metakaolin geopolymerization is performed with sodium hydroxide at a well-defined concentration (Fig. 30). In their work, it was pointed out that zeolites A and X were formed preferentially for relatively low concentration of the activating solution characterized by a Na/Al ratio = 1.18. At relatively high alkaline solution concentrations ($\text{NaAl} = 3.05$), zeolite X

Fig. 29. XRD patterns of the optimal pastes at 90 days, X: Zeolite X = Sodium aluminum silicate hydrate (PDF 01-073-6104 $\text{Na}_{92}(\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_{100}\text{O}_{384})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{100.8}$); A: Zeolite A = Sodium Aluminum Silicate hydrate (PDF 00-039-0222 $\text{Na}_{96}\text{Al}_9\text{Si}_{96}\text{O}_{384}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{216}$); Q: Quartz, syn (PDF 01-079-1910 SiO_2); He: Heulandite-Ca ($(\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_7\text{O}_{18}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O})$ PDF 00-021-0131).

Fig. 30. Update of possible pathways for zeolite A and zeolite X formation as proposed by Onutai [60].

formation was inhibited, while zeolite A was still able to form, but required a longer curing time (over 56 days). In the present study, the Na/Al ratio is 3.19, which, according to previous study [60], should not allow for zeolite X formation. Therefore, the formation of zeolites X and A in the present study may be justified by the Si/Al ratio of 2.66, whereas it was maintained at 1.02 in the previous study [60]. These results may therefore indicate that the nature of the zeolites may not be solely a function of the concentration of the activating solution and the curing time, but that other parameters such as the Si/Al ratio and the curing temperature may also contribute. Therefore, the proposed update of possible pathways of the Zeolite A and Zeolite X formation as previously proposed by Onutai in Fig. 30 may describe better the results of the present study which use higher Si/Al ratios.

The study of Glid *et al.* showed that, for $\text{SiAl} = 1$ and $\text{NaAl} = 1$ ratios, the reaction of metakaolin with sodium hydroxide solution under curing conditions of 90°C at $\text{pH}=13$ mainly led to the formation of zeolite A when the calcination temperature of the kaolin clay was 550°C . However, when the calcination temperature of the kaolin clay was increased to 850°C , zeolite A formation is considerably affected in the short term [7]. On the other hand, geopolymerization in a binary system (MK + slag) does not always seem to lead to zeolite formation. The alkalinity of the reaction medium seems to play an important role. In fact, XRD analysis by Souayfan *et al.* did not reveal the formation of new reaction products except calcite by reaction of MK with a solution of sodium silicate combined with NaOH at 5 mol/l . This is essentially due to amorphous and poorly crystalline character of the reaction products which makes difficult to detect by XRD analysis [61].

Fig. 31. Thermogravimetry analysis of optimal pastes at 90 days.

Fig. 31 shows the results of TGA analysis of optimal pastes at 90 days. TGA analyses reveal a gradual mass loss between 30 and 1000 °C for all pastes, with a total loss of around 24 % for 15CCR paste and 22 % for other pastes. The additional mass loss observed on 15CCR paste occurred at temperatures closer to the decarbonisation of calcites that are located between 550 and 750 °C (weakly crystallized) and between 780 and 1000 °C (strongly crystallized). Furthermore, the calcite peak identified in the pastes containing calcium products is barely visible on 100MK paste and could indicate that the detected calcite could have originated from the base calcium product. Finally, regardless of the calcium product, the Portlandite peak is barely observable in the pastes after 90 days of curing, suggesting its full consumption.

Fig. 32 to Fig. 44 depicts the results of SEM/EDS analysis of the geopolymer pastes. Fig. 45 summarizes the chemistry of the pastes in the CaO–SiO₂–Al₂O₃ ternary diagram. SEM/EDS analysis shows that the microstructure of geopolymer pastes consists of jellified products interspersed with reaction products in the form of tetrahedral granules typical of some zeolites [7,49]. It also reveals the presence of portlandite-type platelets in the pores when MK is substituted by some calcium products. When MK is substituted by 15 % CCR (Fig. 34 - Fig. 37), SEM analysis reveals a less compact structure at 7 days, with hexagonal platelets similar to portlandite at early stage of their formation in the pores. In contrast, XRD and TGA analyses revealed a complete disappearance of portlandite as early as day 28 for all additions containing portlandite at the outset. EDS analyses carried out on these platelets show a homogeneous composition containing at least 30 % Ca associated with at least 10 % Al and traces of Si (≤ 3 %) and Na. As shown in Fig. 32 and Fig. 33, these platelets are non-existent in the pores of the 100MK reference paste, which consists solely of sodium hydroxide-activated metakaolin.

Furthermore, the use of QLM quicklime as a source of calcium in the geopolymer does not lead to the formation of these hexagonal-type platelets. On the contrary, QLM induces the formation of filamentous structures that fully adhere to the structure, thus giving the material a more compact appearance as shown in Fig. 39. These filaments corresponding to the marked zones 593; 594 and 595 in Fig. 43 retain a certain homogeneity marked by a relatively high calcium composition (≈ 20 %) compared to the average (marked zones 596; 597; 598; 599) where the average amount of calcium is less than 10 %.

Overall, EDS analysis of the gels projected onto the CaO–Al₂O₃–SiO₂ pseudo-ternary diagram in Fig. 46 shows that reaction products can be classified into 3 main groups. Group 1, characterized by a fairly homogeneous structure and a relatively low calcium content, is encountered in the vast majority of pastes analyzed. Their composition is similar to that of low-Ca C-(N)-A-S-H gels, as observed in similar studies [62–64]. Their structure is similar to that of the N-A-S-H type gel found in the calcium-free 100MK reference paste. This first group, although

Fig. 33. SEM analysis of 100MK paste at 90 days (x500).

Fig. 34. SEM analysis of 15CCR paste at 7 days (x1000).

Fig. 35. SEM analysis of 15CCR paste at 90 days (x500).

Fig. 32. SEM analysis of 100MK paste at 90 days (x2000).

fairly compact, reveals a shift towards the CaO peak (to the left) of the reaction products when the amount of mobilizable calcium is more consistent in the initial raw material. Thus, after the 100MK gel represented by marking zone 524 on the ternary diagram, we can observe a first sub-group made up of reaction products from 15CCR (zone 610) and 100PC (zone 548). The second subgroup is made up of the marking zones of 10QLM (zones 597; 598), and 10SLM (zone 444), gels marked by a higher calcium content. As a reminder, Table 1 shows that CCR and

Fig. 36. SEM analysis of 15CCR paste at 90 days (x 2000).

Fig. 39. SEM analysis of 10QLM paste at 90 days (x 3000).

Fig. 37. SEM analysis of 15CCR paste at 90 days (x 3000).

Fig. 38. SEM analysis of 10SLM paste at 90 days (x 1000).

Their high calcium content, combined with alumina and silicon, brings them closer to C-(A)-S-H type gels [29] than to portlandite. The formation of C-(N)-A-S-H and C-(A)-S-H gels could be responsible for the development of geopolymer strength.

The group 3 of reaction products consists of hexagonal structures found mainly in the pores (Fig. 34-Fig. 38; Fig. 39; Fig. 41; Fig. 43 and Fig. 43). Their chemical composition reveals a calcium content of around 40 %, combined with around 10 % aluminum. They are found exclusively in cases where MK is substituted by CCR, SLM and OPC. A projection of their composition on the CaO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂ ternary diagram shows that they are close to portlandite. However, as they retain a certain homogeneity in terms of their aluminum (≥ 10 %) and silicon (≤ 5 %) content, it would be inaccurate to consider them as portlandite, whose chemical composition contains neither silica nor aluminum.

On the other hand, portlandite is known to combine with MK to form calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) (Eqs. 1 and 2). However, the reaction products' chemistry through SEM/EDS analysis did not reveal the presence of such structures; the 3 groups of reaction products identified in the gels being relatively distant from the C-S-Hs as identified in previous studies [29]. The hexagonal platelets observed could therefore be an alteration of portlandite in a strongly alkaline environment. This hypothesis is in line with the results of previous XRD and TGA analyses, which showed a gradual disappearance of portlandite over time, and its total disappearance by the 90th day in cases where it had initially been identified.

The microcalorimetry results in Fig. 46 show that the exothermic peak appears quickly on the 100MK reference paste compared to MK substituted pastes. The peak appeared around 4h30 minutes after the activator solution and metakaolin powder were mixed. The heat flow reaches 7 mW/g at 4h30 minutes for this paste. Substitution of MK by calcium-rich products leads to a significant decrease in heat flow; which

Fig. 40. Relative composition of 100MK paste at 90 days.

OPC contained relatively the same amounts of CaO (60.1 and 54.4 % respectively), while QLM and SLM contained relatively higher amounts (more than 74.8 %). This difference shows that, although the reaction products are broadly similar in nature, the amount of mobilizable calcium initially contained in the raw materials could have an influence on the degree of calcium involvement in the reaction products.

The group 2 of essentially represents reaction products from the fibrous zone when QLM is used as a substitute for MK (Fig. 39; Fig. 42).

Fig. 41. Relative composition of 15CCR paste at 90 days.

Fig. 42. Relative composition of 10QLM paste at 90 days.

Fig. 43. Relative composition of 10OPC paste at 90 days.

Fig. 44. Relative composition of 10SLM paste at 90 days.

Fig. 45. Projection of the geopolymer material's chemistry onto the ternary CaO-SiO₂-Al₂O₃ system, showing elemental compositions of the optimal pastes as measured by SEM-EDS after 90 curing days.

stabilizes at 4, 3, 2.8, and 2.6 mW/g respectively for pastes containing 10QLM, 10SLM, 10OPC, and 15CCR; after 10h30 minutes, 13h00 minutes, 15h45 minutes, and 16h05 minutes respectively. These peaks are generally wider than the peak observed on the 100MK reference paste, showing an almost instantaneous reaction for the reference paste. This corroborates the observation on compressive strengths, where the reference concrete seems to reach its optimum performance at a relatively short curing age (as early as day 14).

In addition, although the substitution of MK by calcium products showed an overall reduction in heat release, there are notable differences in the way each of these calcium products reacts over time. The 10QLM quicklime paste reached a peak heat flow of 4 mW/g, representing around 54 % more than the heat released by 15CCR; 43 % more than 10OPC; and 33 % more than 10SLM pastes. It can also be seen that these exothermic peaks become wider as the amount of heat released is reduced. This leads to less pronounced gaps in the overall heat released during the first 95 hours than those observed in the heat flow diagram. Thus, the cumulative heat released over the first 95 hours stabilizes at 460, 412, 403, 402 and 380 j/g respectively for 100MK, 10QLM, 10OPC, 10SLM and 15CCR pastes. The cumulative heat released by 10QLM is only 2 % higher than the cumulative heat released by 10SLM and 10OPC, and 8 % higher than 15CCR. This is due to a broader exothermic peak observed on the heat flow diagram. CCR stands out from the other products for its low cumulative heat release. Considering the sensitivity of geopolymerization reactions to heat, this low cumulative heat release could be both a cause and a consequence of the low dissolution rate of aluminosilicate in the reaction medium. It may be concluded that the substitution of MK by calcium products leads to an extension of the exothermic reaction time, rather than an increase in the total amount of heat released. Although the peak heat flow is reduced, it is much more spread out over time, resulting in longer curing of the pastes, which is more beneficial for the development of mechanical strength, compared with the reference paste characterized by high heat emission over a shorter period.

Furthermore, like quicklime, cement hydration is an exothermic reaction which should normally lead to an increase in total heat released. The reduction in the cumulative heat release is due to the fact that cement hydration is strongly inhibited in alkaline media, as observed in previous studies. Martinez-Ramirez and Palomo observed that when cement hydration took place in an alkaline medium composed of 10 M NaOH solution, the total heat released was halved compared to when hydration took place with distilled water [52,53]. Although their observations were made exclusively in a pure cement hydration situation, it cannot be ruled out that the same phenomenon is transposable to the case of geopolymerization, where other reactions besides the hydration

Fig. 46. Microcalorimetry analysis of the optimal pastes (for 1 g of geopolymer paste).

of cement take place.

Finally, the microcalorimetry results are in accordance with the results of FTIR, XRD and mechanical analysis: the more heat the calcium product tends to release during the reaction, the faster the geopolymerization reactions and vice versa. The quicker the reactions, the higher the early age compressive strengths. The highlights of the mechanical and microstructural characteristics of the geopolymer concrete with optimal content of each calcium-addition are summarized in Table 3.

4. Conclusions and perspectives

The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of the addition of different calcium products on the mechanical and microstructural properties of metakaolin-based geopolymer concrete cured under sub-Saharan room-temperature. The results indicated that:

- The addition of calcium products leads to an improvement in mechanical strengths during the ambient curing of geopolymer concrete. However, the nature of the substitute calcium product seems to have a significant impact on early-age mechanical strengths. QLM

(quicklime) seems to have an overall accelerating effect on early age strength development, while CCR (calcium carbide residue) causes a general slowdown. SLM (hydrated lime) and OPC (cement) have a mixed effect: for substitution rates below 15 %, there is a slowdown, while higher rates accelerate the formation of reaction products.

- Microcalorimetry analysis reveals that the substitution of MK by calcium products leads to an overall decrease in cumulative heat release. This phenomenon is accompanied by an overall shift and enlargement of the exothermic peak, resulting in more prolonged curing of the pastes and consequently greater mechanical strength. The more heat the calcium product tends to release, the faster the geopolymerization reactions and vice versa.
- Infrared analysis revealed that CCR and OPC cement delayed the formation of certain reaction products, compared with QLM quicklime, where all the zeolites' peaks observed at 90 days were present since day 7.
- XRD analysis reveals the formation of two types of zeolites in the structure: zeolite A and zeolite X. However, depending on the nature of the addition, one would be formed in preference to the other. When MK is substituted by CCR, zeolite X is the first to form, unlike zeolite A, whose peaks are only strongly present from day 90. For the

Table 3

Summary of the main results.

Calcium-rich material	Metakaolin:	Calcium carbide residue	Quicklime	Slacked lime	Portland cement
Optimal content (%)	100 % MK (reference)	15 % CCR	5–10 % QLM	10 % SLM	10–15 % OPC
Compressive strength	28 days 14.5 MPa	19 MPa	23.5 MPa	18.7 MPa	27.5 MPa
	90 days 14.5 MPa	31 MPa	30 MPa	22 MPa	31.3 MPa
Cumulative heat (j/g)	460	380	412	402	403
Peak heat flow (mW/g)	7	2.6	4	3	2.8
Main reaction products	- N-A-S-H gel - Zeolite A (well-crystallized) - Zeolite X (well-crystallized)	- N-A-S-H and Low-Ca C-A-S-H gels - Zeolite A - Zeolite X - Calcites Portlandite-like platelets (except QLM)			
Positive impact	- Rapid formation of reaction products without carbonates	- Enhancement of long-term mechanical performances	- High mechanical performance at early age - Acceleration of the formation of reaction products - Highest amount of heat	- Rapid formation of reactions' products - Enhance the mechanical performances	- Enhancement of the mechanical performances
Negative impact	- Lowest mechanical performance - Porous structure	- Low mechanical performance at early age - Delay effect on geopolymerization - Lowest amount of heat	- Excessive desiccation beyond 10 % QLM	- Relatively low mechanical performance	- Low mechanical performance at early age - Delay effect on geopolymerization at early age

other calcium products, zeolite A is the first to form, while zeolite X has peaks only detectable from the 28th day.

- SEM/EDS analysis showed that the overall structure of the binder was similar to that of low-Ca C(N)-A-S-H. It also revealed zeolite granules, as well as hexagonal (portlandite-like) and filamentous singularities, depending on the nature of the calcium product.
- FTIR analysis revealed that certain calcium product reacts more quickly than others. For instance, all the major chemical bonds are formed as early as 7 days in the pastes containing QLM whereas other calcium products such as CCR, SLM, and OPC had delayed the formation of certain Si-O-Al bonds which start to be clearly visible only after 28 days of maturation.

Other analyses such as ²⁹Si MAS NMR and ²⁷Al MAS NMR could help to understand the configuration of atomic bonds in the geopolymer pastes in general and within some singularities such as the hexagonal portlandite-like platelets and the fibrous patterns identified in the SEM/EDS analysis. The durability of such materials may also be investigated in order to provide data for their application in engineering structures.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Adamah MESSAN: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Gilles ESCADEILLAS:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Seick Omar SORE:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Philbert NSHIMIYIMANA:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Yawo Daniel ADUFU:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: NSHIMIYIMANA Philbert reports financial support was provided by World Bank Group. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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